

Identity and the Acquisition of Language

This essay points in some unfamiliar directions, so an initial orientation will help. You need to distinguish your mental identity from your physical identity, and to accept that your mental identity ('you') has been socially constructed and is *not* inherited. It is the link between this aspect of the identity and language that must be explained.

I will describe what makes human brains together distinctly human; *together* because the quality of being human cannot be accounted for by analysing one brain. The meaning of the term identity will become clear, but it is also what is referred to when people speak of human 'consciousness', intending by that term something unique to us that other animals do not possess (although animals are perfectly conscious). Our human identities are the result of the activity of a brain matrix that develops from scratch, grows, ages and eventually begins to fail. I have called this matrix 'thinkish' because it is the brain activity that generates our speech, thoughts and minds. My task here is to model thinkish in simple terms. A clear account is never a guarantee that it is the correct one, but clarity will certainly help critics - although I am pretty sure that the principles of what I am going to say are sound; working out scientifically how the brain satisfies these principles is a different ball game.

The following graphic is unlikely to make it into the neuroanatomy textbooks, but it will get things started.

I have represented thinkish as a discrete area in the brain but this is just for convenience. I have no reason to suppose that thinkish has an architecture that confines it to a local area of the brain and there is no reason in principle why thinkish activity should not involve all those areas of the brain so highly developed in humans. The red arrows are intended to signify routines of activity between the members of families of neurones, the families themselves being interconnected, forming a 'matrix'. The use of arrows is intended to indicate *activity*. The activity is not chaotic, it is organised into

routines. Thinkish routines have generated speech in the graphic, but if the sounds had been retained and thought rather than spoken I would have used a 'thought bubble' coming out of the brain.

The thinkish matrix indicated in the graphic is the adult one (let's say), but we are not born with the matrix in place, so I have to include in a model the process by which the matrix begins, grows and develops in a young brain. I can make an important point straight away: thinkish begins from nothing. To understand this idea, think about the brain learning to ride a bike. (I am going to talk about the brain as if the body was simply a hanger-on.) Nobody is surprised that the brain learns to ride a bike from nothing – it can't ride a bike, and then it can; it learns and keeps a 'ride-a-bike' matrix of neural activity. Thinkish is operating on the same principle, and the thinkish matrix is what the brain acquires as it learns to 'ride' language. You will see that I am equating the bikes that children will be given and the language that they will be given. Obviously there is much more to explain and at this point I will just say that the ride-a-bike example was chosen for a reason.

Each of us has two identities: a physical identity and a social identity. The physical identity is constructed, to use that word again, more-or-less according to the instructions of the genes, and it includes the body part that I am discussing: the brain. The social identity results from a matrix of brain activity that has been 'socially constructed' over a life-time, not by the genes but by language. (Language as a 'constructor' is going to take some explaining.) The mind is the active expression of the social identity, and it's the boss, the last decision-maker in the chain of command: the brain that defends the physical identity of its owner could never issue instructions to terminate itself; the social identity/mind could. The human brain has to manage these two identities together, keep them both safe and well, and no other animal has the same problem to the same degree. The physical identity is managed and kept safe by an individual's brain, using reflexes and emotions; in this sense we are animals like any other. As creatures with bodies, there is no difference in principle between us and other animals and it is worth bearing in mind that their physical pain and suffering is no different to ours. What marks us out as very special and quite unlike other animals, is the social identity. There are other social animals of course, but not like us. Ants, for example, are social animals, but an individual ant has a simple, rigid, inherited identity, quite unlike the unique, complex and autonomous identity that we each acquire and are in some measure free to create. This identity is what thinkish is all about. Thinkish is the active matrix in our 'animal' brain that solves the problem of creating and keeping safe a social identity, thereby making it a human brain.

How does the human brain create a physical and a social identity together in the same head? I have illustrated the principle of how it works below, and I have used two terms to describe brain activity: 'presentation' and 'representation'. The idea is simple: the 'animal' aspect of the brain constructs a presentation of the physical world, including its owner's body, just like any other animal with a sophisticated brain; and mental

activity, the neural activity of our minds in action, constructs representations. So the physical identity takes the form of a *presentation* in the brain that is constructed using the information from the senses; the social identity is an active *representation* constructed by the operation of language; the mind is the expression of the representation at any moment.

The brain creates a presentation from the information it gets from its senses and from its owner's body (the red arrows); for example, one part of the presentation would be 'visual' and another part would be 'body movement routines'. The brain has a long evolutionary history that has put in place the mechanisms for creating a presentation of the physical world that works in practice: a presentation is essentially a valid map of the physical world that keep us, like other animals, alive and reproducing. This presentation is the *brain's version of reality* and it is from this brain activity that we get the feeling of what is certain and 'natural' to us; this is the common sense reality of an animal with senses that feels alive. (This much we surely share with other animals with relatively sophisticated brains). The brain's presentation is the seat of the emotions - and of the existential feelings that it is so difficult to philosophise about because they are not in language. Note that the 'animal' aspect of the brain does not have a presentation of *itself*; there is no animal-I. The brain is the defender of the solitary animal, so why would it need a mirror that serves no purpose? However, the human aspect of the brain is not solitary, it is social and the social brain *does* need a mirror for the identity of its owner, and now we are getting back to...

The human brain has the capacity to inspect some aspects of the presentation by 'paying attention'. This mental activity creates re-presentations of the presentation. Vision can be used as an illustration: the eye and brain together see the real world just as any animal would, but the brain can then inspect mentally the visual presentation and 'represent' what it is paying attention to. ("I see" says the mind.) However, I am begging the question with the example of vision, because to generate the mind that is 'seeing' the brain's visual presentation, the thinkish matrix is necessary. It is by the activity in this matrix that the mind is generated, in other words the mind that 'sees', thinks or speaks. The expressed form of mental activity is symbolic language, usually

natural but, for some people, mathematical or musical too. Mental representations are the *mind's version of reality* (“I see!”, again). So it is possible to say that the human brain doesn't just house the two identities, physical and social, it has two models of reality, the 'animal' model constructed from the senses, and the mental model constructed with language. What it is possible to understand by the term 'reality' is therefore constrained by the properties of the senses on the one hand and language on the other; but in both cases the arbiter for reality is 'whatever works'.

The contrast between the two versions of reality enables me to draw attention to a long-standing problem of method that has created a fundamental issue in describing the way the brain functions. Representations result from the operation of language and its symbols. The mind is a symbol-juggler, and 'meaning' in language has been condensed into symbols and their relationship. We take a symbol to be a stable repository of meaning that functions as if it was permanent, not evanescent – take the word 'consciousness', for example, a 'thing' we just can't quite seem to get hold of. From the brain's down-to-earth point of view, the mind lives in Cloud Concept Land. The trick, at least in the first instance, is to think like a brain.

To explain the relationship between brain and language, I need to make several points that stem from the fact that brains handle information. The brain uses information from the senses and from its owner's body to create a presentation of the physical world - and language plays no part in this process. Since language is chock-full of information, it might seem an odd thing to say, but it leads to the second point: thinkish is not itself a language. Thinkish is the activity of an acquired brain presentation that can recognise and generate sounds that have proved to be meaningful in communication. This means that I will have to explain the link between the brain activity of the thinkish matrix, which is not language, and the meaningful language that we speak and think. The third point: I must make it clear how the brain has been able to solve the challenge of handling language with the means at its disposal – those of the 'animal' brain. The human brain has evolved as a unit with the human body and solved the problem of information-handling peculiar to human beings by adapting what it already had as an 'animal' brain; it has not created any functions that are fundamentally new. What *is* fundamentally new, and explains the success of the species, has come from the social interaction of individual autonomous brains by means of language. It is social interaction that provides the multiplication factor of our otherwise limited individual capabilities. Nevertheless, each tiny brain had to be up to the job, so how did it and how does it acquire language?

Experienced physical reality is the brain's primordial concern, so the first step is to consider the physical basis of language and communication: the brains of two individuals linked by sound. Starting from this point, it is clear that the brain was equipped to deal with the physical aspect of language long before language became what we understand it to be now. The model of thinkish must be based on the way the brain reacts to the physical aspects of the sound of the voice. You can see that treating

human communication at this level is relevant to the question of both the evolutionary acquisition of language and of its appearance 'from nothing' in every infant brain.

So how does the brain deal with the sound of the voice? The ear has a mechanism for receiving the *movement* of the air caused by a voice and converting the *movements* of vibrations into nerve impulses. I have used italics for emphasis because the sound of the voice is dealt with in terms of a process that the brain does understand: physical movement. There are obviously other features of the voice that are important, so I must at some point refer to the voice not just as a moving stream of sound, but as a form of music. Just for the moment though I will concentrate on the essential problem that the brain has: 'understanding' movement. Remember, the brain doesn't think with concepts like 'movement', that's the mind's language game. The brain has had to find an aspect of its presentation of the physical world that will give both *practical* meaning to the movements of the sound of the voice and a means of remembering them.

What presentation has the brain got that 'embodies' the principle of movement?

I have indicated here the principle (and definitely not the neuroanatomy) of the presentation of body movements in this dancer's brain – a presentation that would include somewhere her ability to ride a bike. The choreographic routines of the brain's presentation of its owner's body movements provide the reference frame with which our animal brains 'understand' and remember movement.

So the brain possesses an ancestral presentation for processing the physical movement of the music of the voice. The brain's presentation of movement of the body is the substrate for the thinkish matrix and is the basis for understanding the effect the voice.

The brain reacts to the musical sound of language by cross-matching the perceived movement of sounds to its presentation of movements of the body of its owner, to its movement matrix. You could say that those red arrows in the thinkish matrix represent interconnected song-and-dance routines. The first values carried by these routines do not represent 'meaning' in the sense of language; I'll get to that next. They are deeper values because they are part of the brain's physical presentation and are therefore tightly linked to the emotions and feelings. The human voice has a profound emotional influence on the human brain, critical in the process of acquisition of language and largely overlooked in the hurley-burley of adult daily life.

I must now explain how the 'musical' communication between human beings is organised so that it means something. Communication in language involves reliable transfer of information, meaning and values. Neural song-and-dance routines must work beyond the touchy-feely values that I have given them if they are responsible for receiving and generating language. In the upper part of the next graphic I have indicated a brain generating a stream of sound. It could be the brain of a three year-old in the process of emitting a stream of sounds just as if it were language but which is in reality a kind of musical gobbledegook; this happens, it is not unusual. Equally well, it could be the brain of an adult emitting the sounds of meaningful language; the process is the same.

The second part of the graphic illustrates what is absolutely essential if spoken sounds are to be meaningful: meaning arises from the successful use in communication of the sound output generated by the thinkish matrix. What does it take for success? If a routine doesn't work, it fades away and if it does work, it is reinforced and forms part of thinkish. The brain routines that have proved to be meaningful in communication are retained because they successfully provide the meaning of a word or concept. Routines generate the corresponding stream of signs and bingo! they work in practical terms; that is to say $E = Mc^2$ works in practice in the physical world and "I love you" works (sometimes) in the social world. The routines that generated these expressions are therefore successful and useful in some way. The brain does not store 'sound' or 'meaning' or any other abstraction, it stores neural routines of the type: 'song and dance'. The acquired properties of these routines give the ability to understand language and their output gives an individual the ability to speak and think.

I can explain the idea of 'song and dance' more precisely by treating the song element as sensory input to the brain and the dance element as the motor output in response. The following graphic illustrates how the two principles 'sensory' and 'motor' are important in the infant brain at the stage when language is being acquired.

You can see from the layout that sensory inputs act as constructors. Neurones that are not initially set in their function receive the information from the sensory input and collectively become sensory *and* motor. The result is a 'sensorimotor' matrix and in the graphic I have put the initial sensory component on top of the resulting motor component.

The sound of the voice is the key for acquiring language and some of the blank sheet neurones 'sense' the sound of the voice (the song element of the 'song and dance'). The songs then guide the development of associated neurones that become motor in function, capable of driving the production of vocal sounds (the equivalent of the dance). When the system is ready to tango...

My question was picked up by those sensory elements in your acquired thinkish matrix that recognised its meaning, these elements triggered activity in a host of other 'experienced' elements that mistakenly interpreted my intentions, and you passed up on the chance of a lifetime. Hopefully you get the important point though: in the same way that sensory input is a 'constructor' for organising the choreography of the musculoskeletal system, the sound of the voice becomes the 'constructor' of the thinkish matrix. The thinkish matrix then develops by acquiring and reinforcing routines that are successful in communication. The early sensorimotor wobbles become the ability to ride the language bike, the thinkish matrix becomes the social identity and the expression of the social identity in language is the mind.

Summary

We are social animals. Searching inside the head of one individual will not resolve the problem of the human identity or explain the way language works. This approach is what is known as a category error: the mind cannot be reduced to the neuronal connexions in one brain. It can only be understood in terms of the successful *use* of neural routines established during the lifetime of the individual. Meaning is 'whatever works' in communication (and reality is 'whatever works', full stop.)

Forget genetics: think 'social construction'. If you think you are a member of an oppressed 'race' or a member of a 'superior' one, forget that too; the label 'race' should simply never be used to describe the identity of a human being (nor any physical characteristic). Much better to look at it this way: if you are a member of an oppressed *culture*, you have probably been fed the *language* of oppression and maybe resentment; if you are a member of a *culture* of excellence, you will have been fed the *language* of achievement and maybe over-expectation. The process of social construction of the mind is responsible for, and explains very well, all the aspects of the identity that mysteriously 'feel part of' the individual. The principle of social construction of our

minds is straightforward: the transmission between individuals and generations of values, attitudes, knowledge, skills, entertaining myths... and downright lies.

Thinkish is an acquired 'matrix' in the brain. It is unique to each individual and constructed over the life-time by the process of acquisition (and loss) of information. The expressed activity of the matrix is the mind. The early matrix is usually 'constructed' by the sound of voices but there is no reason in principle why any sensory input that signals human contact should not operate similarly. Where is thinkish in the brain? One clue may be the slowness of thinking (compared to nerve impulse propagation): putting thoughts together resembles the activity of a cross-talking social network in the brain much more than the concentrated activity of a brain 'centre'. It is possible that thinkish involves pretty much all of the brain.

Thinkish activity is a choreography of acquired rules. These rules are a version of the universal rules that apply to the reliable transfer and storage of information and values - and brains have had their own inherited versions of them ever since there were brains in animals. It is understandable that rules apply to language, but 'rules of communication' must also have been acquired to create thinkish. A tap on the head that prevents the brain from following them would disrupt thinkish and result in loss of the mind and awareness even if the individual neurones concerned were still firing away. To produce this essay, my thinkish activity had to follow the rules: it had to impel a narrative, employ symbols and have a context. The context is my personal history of thinking about the mind. The symbols take the form of 'framed pictures' of packets of information that I recall. The narrative is the act of stringing these pictures together and can constitute my thoughts and be converted into the virtual voice of this text only because thinkish activity consists of these principles. The 'narrative' of a thought looks very much like the traffic between different parts of the brain (slow), and those brain parts may be groups of neurones in habitual contact with each other that form picture-symbols (time-saving).

The Big Language Bang. Human beings are the result of evolution; and the mechanism underlying evolution is genetics. However. The success of this species, a social species above all else, is the result of a step change in the evolutionary process. We stumbled across – because that's how evolution works – a new way of processing and sharing information about who we think we are and what we think the world we live in is like. We have been the beneficiaries of the Big Language Bang (on an evolutionary time scale). With the emergence of this species, the pace of evolution changed dramatically from the slow flow of the stream of physical evolution to a torrent of cultural change. Cultural change may well seem slow from the perspective of one's life-span or a history book, but relatively, it has been a stampede. In comparison to the rate of cultural change, we, as individuals, are not evolving physically in any fundamental way. Human populations can still evolve genetically to some extent – in response to virus pandemics, for example – but the capability of the human brain is not going to change. We are going to have to work with what we have got to respond to the

challenge of understanding and managing cultural change, the future of the species and, as it has turned out, the future of the planet; hence the importance of understanding 'what we have got'. It seems that there is only one way: putting our heads together.

